

Data Mining and Text Analysis of Spanish Declassified UFO Military Records (1962–1995): A Preprint Summary

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Abstract

This work summarizes a reproducible data-mining pipeline applied to the full corpus of UFO sighting records declassified by the Spanish Air Force and held at the Biblioteca Virtual de Defensa (BVMDefensa). The source catalogue contained 82 documents; 79 were sighting case files included in the database (78 canonical cases after excluding one duplicate). The corpus spans 2,135 pages (1962–1995) after OCR. The pipeline comprises: (1) automated scraping and download of the digital catalogue; (2) dual OCR (Apple Vision and olmOCR on cloud GPU) with automatic best-source selection per document and domain-specific cleaning; (3) normalization, geocoding, and loading into a relational database (SQLite); (4) heuristic extraction of 8 fields from summaries and 12 from full text (cause, witness type, object shape/color/motion, etc.), using regex and a local LLM where needed; (5) quantitative analysis—multilingual semantic embeddings (Sentence-Transformers), UMAP, HDBSCAN clustering, lexical statistics, temporal and radar vs. non-radar comparisons; (6) a knowledge graph built from triplets extracted with a local language model and community detection. Ground-truth corrections were applied to erroneous metadata (Canarias, Talavera, Manises). Main results: heterogeneous temporal distribution (peak in 1968), predominance of civilian (31.7%) and tower (21.5%) observers, one dominant semantic cluster (35.4% of documents), cause identified in 62% of cases (Venus, balloon, optical phenomena). Fusion with olmOCR greatly improved coverage for duration (24% to 79%) and photograph (15% to 60%). A RAG system over the full text index (6,460 chunks) with default model qwen2.5:7b validates retrieval of known historical cases. The pipeline and database are an open, auditable resource for further research on unidentified aerial phenomena in Spain.

Keywords: data mining, UFO, UAP, declassified records, OCR, NLP, semantic embeddings, knowledge graph, UMAP, HDBSCAN, Spain, BVMDefensa.

1 Introduction

The release of military files on unidentified aerial phenomena (UAP/UFO) has been gradual in several countries [Clarke, 2015, COMETA, 1999, ODNI, 2021]. In Spain, declassification was driven by the Air Force Operational Command (MOA) between 1992 and 1999 [Ballester Olmos, 2016, 2017]. The records, covering sightings from 1962 to 1995, were digitized and made public via the Ministry of Defence’s Biblioteca Virtual de Defensa (BVMDefensa) [BVMDefensa, 2024]. Prior work on this corpus has been largely qualitative or case-by-case. This project provides a *computational* pipeline that turns the full corpus into a structured, queryable database and applies NLP and quantitative analytics to characterize it.

2 Scope and methods

2.1 Data source and corpus

The corpus is the “Expedientes OVNI” section of BVMDDefensa. The downloaded catalogue had 82 documents; 79 are sighting case files (78 canonical after marking one Manises duplicate). Three PDFs (regulations, interview, general report) were excluded. Each case has catalog metadata, geographic fields, and extracted text (summary and, where available, full report, considerations, and other sections).

2.2 Pipeline overview

Figure 1 summarizes the end-to-end architecture. Processing is sequential: (1) fetch catalogue index and per-case metadata (HTML/JSON); (2) normalize dates and locations; (3) load into SQLite (`casos`, `caso_geopoints`, `caso_textos`); (4) download source PDFs/images; (5) optional steps: populate from HTML, geocode (Nominatim + defence facilities dictionary), fill region. Then: dual OCR (Apple Vision + olmOCR, cloud GPU), build a *fused* corpus by choosing the best OCR source per document (olmOCR selected for 96% of cases), clean text with a domain dictionary (reducing unrecognized-word rate from 40.4% to 13.2%), ingest summaries and full text into `caso_textos`, and extract structured fields.

Figure 1: Full pipeline: from source (BVMDDefensa) through acquisition, dual OCR and fusion, relational storage (SQLite), structured field extraction, semantic embeddings and clustering, knowledge-graph construction, and retrieval-augmented generation (RAG).

2.3 Ground-truth and field extraction

Metadata errors (wrong `date_year` for Canarias, Talavera, Manises) were corrected from historical references; one duplicate was flagged. From *summaries*, 8 fields were extracted (observer type, time, duration, radar, photograph, place, etc.); from *full text* (fused corpus), 12 more (declassification date, document count, posterior investigation, proposed explanation, identified cause, object shape/color/motion, weather, witness profession, etc.) via regex and, for cause, a local LLM (Ollama) with a controlled vocabulary.

2.4 Quantitative analysis and RAG

Semantic embeddings (paraphrase-multilingual-MiniLM-L12-v2, 384 dims) were computed on summaries; UMAP for 2D/3D; HDBSCAN for clustering; lexical stats (tokens, bigrams, TTR); temporal distribution and radar vs. non-radar comparison. A *knowledge graph* was built from triplets extracted with a local model (Ollama), with community detection (Girvan–Newman). A *RAG* system (ChromaDB, same embeddings, 6,460 chunks from all text types) retrieves top-*k* chunks and generates answers via a local LLM; the default model (qwen2.5:7b) was chosen after a comparative experiment over five models on five difficult questions.

3 Results

Table 1 summarizes the database. Figure 2 shows the heterogeneous temporal distribution (1962–1995), with a strong peak in 1968 (22.2% of cases) and the share of cases in the dominant cluster per year. Geocoding succeeded for 72 of 79 cases (91.1%); their locations are shown in Figure 3. Observer types: civilian 31.7%, tower 21.5%, pilot 17.8%, military ground 11.5%. One dominant HDBSCAN cluster contains 35.4% of documents; the rest are smaller clusters or noise. Figure 4 displays the UMAP 2D projection of semantic embeddings coloured by cluster. Figure 5 shows the three-dimensional knowledge-graph visualization (ForceAtlas2 layout in the XY plane, node degree on the Z axis; main cluster elevated, peripheral nodes at the base; communities coloured, edges in light blue). Cause is identified in 62% of cases (Venus, balloon, optical phenomenon, etc.). Adding the fused corpus (olmOCR) dramatically increased coverage for duration (24% to 79%) and photograph (15% to 60%). The RAG system, tested on four historical ground-truth questions (Manises 1979, Canarias/Atrevida 1976, Talavera 1976, Valencia scramble), reconstructs the expected events in three of four queries (Reconstruct) and partially in the fourth.

Table 1: Database and corpus summary.

Metric	Value
Documents in source catalogue	82
Sighting cases in DB	79
Canonical cases (no duplicate)	78
Pages (post-OCR)	2,135
With geographic coordinates	72 (91.1%)
With summary in DB	79 (100%)
RAG index (chunks, all text types)	6,460
Identified cause (from full-text extraction)	62%
Dominant semantic cluster (HDBSCAN)	35.4%

Figure 2: Temporal distribution of cases (bars, left axis) and % of cases per year in the dominant HDBSCAN cluster (line, right axis). The 1968 peak and varying cluster share show heterogeneous temporal and semantic structure.

Figure 3: Map of case locations (72 geocoded). Spain (mainland and Balearic Islands) and Canarias. Colour gradient indicates year of the event (older to more recent).

Figure 4: UMAP 2D projection of semantic embeddings (78 summaries). Points coloured by HDBSCAN cluster; one dominant cluster (35.4% of documents) and smaller clusters or noise illustrate non-homogeneous semantic structure.

Figure 5: Three-dimensional visualization of the knowledge graph. The XY plane uses the ForceAtlas2 layout; the Z axis represents node degree (higher degree, higher altitude). The main cluster rises vertically; peripheral nodes of lower degree and other communities sit at the base. Nodes coloured by community; edges in light blue.

4 Conclusion

The project delivers a reproducible pipeline from the Spanish BVMDefensa UFO catalogue to a structured SQLite database, dual-OCR fused corpus, 20+ extracted fields, semantic and lexical analytics, a knowledge graph, and a RAG system validated on historical cases. The database, code, and documentation are intended as an open, auditable resource for further computational research on declassified UAP records in Spain. Limitations include the small sample size (78 cases), heuristic extraction without full manual validation, and dependence on OCR and embedding quality; RAG answers require optional verification. A similar methodology is currently being developed for a multi-database project including NUFORC [NUFORC, 2026], UFOCAT [CUFOS, 2026], and GEIPAN [CNES, 2026]; the present work serves as a smaller-scale benchmark to verify the methods before scaling to those larger corpora.

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